

HEAVY METAL IONS: NEW IDEOLOGIES FOR THE PRODUCTION OF GENETICALLY MODIFIED PLANT FORMS

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Under normal condition plant system supports cooperation among tissues and organs and actively uses trophic and energy resources. The determination of any external factor provoker a number changes within organism. Those changes are symptoms of stress setuation. Stress desturbes plant parameters up to their full destruction.

Among abiotic stresses the osmotic stress is the most dangerous one. It is explained by various stress – related genes and products expression. That is why the dynamics of tolerance mechanisms depends on coordinated expression of genes network. So abiotic stress tolerance is combined nature and thus comparatively difficult to obtaine tolerant varieties [1].

Several eflorts are being made to improve plant stress tolerance chrongh cell selection. Various plants forms with improved peculiar features were obtained via cell selection.

In general HMI can product vast pathological alterations in diflerent tissues of plant organism. From the other hand, the tolerance to HMI and osmotic stress may by combined. It is

known, that the principal injury of salinity pressure is connected with irreversible loss of internal K^+ ions. From the other hand Ba^{2+} cations can destroy the transfer of K^+ streams [2, 3].

Plant deprivation disturbs plants protein compartments. Water plant status is connected with different types of proteins. The LEA (late embryogenesis abundant proteins) are among them. Some stress factors, especially cadmium, Cd^{2+} , inhibit synthesis and accumulation of LEA. So we use Cd^{2+} in cell selection for increase plant tolerance. There is a new trend of cell selection that provides the opportunity for obtaining variants with combined tolerance [6, 8].

Selective systems with lethal for cell cultures of wild type doses of Ba^{2+} and Cd^{2+} cations were elaborated. Tobacco cell suspension cultures were planted in Petri dishes between two layers of selective media. Lethal doses of HMI resulted in elimination of wild type cells. Only single cell with genetic changes keep their viability. Ion – resistant cells grow on selective media and formed resistant cell lines. Ba – resistant lines were cultivated in presence of Ba^{2+} cations; Cd^{2+} – resistant variants were cultivated under Cd^{2+} stress pressure. After several passages (single passage continued 30 – 35 days) under such initial conditions experimental cell variants were transferred to media with salinity or mannitol. Salinity was simulated by addition of sea water salts. Mannitol is organic compounds for simulating water deficit. Toxic agents were added at lethal doses. Ba – resistant and Cd – resistant cell lines maintained viability under osmotic stress pressure. So new cell cultures exhibited combined stress resistant [5, 7, 9].

From cell lines with combined stress resistant tobacco plants and progeny were obtained. In many cases regenerants from tolerant cell cultures had not high level of stress tolerance. But regenerants of tobacco, obtained in our experiments, demonstrated active viability under osmotic stress pressure *in vitro*. This event is the argument for genetic character of feature.

Plant growth and development under osmotic stress pressure depend on activation of cascades of biochemical osmotic/gene products. Free L – proline its synthesis/accumulation/degradation are good marker of organism viability both under normal or stress conditions. L – proline is a peculiar amino acid. Its synthesis/degradation is managed by own enzyme systems [4].

Osmotic stresses cause a wide range of disorders. Therefore, osmotolerance is associated with changes in the complex maintenance of vital activity. Proline can play the role of a nonspecific stress protector, by virtue of its half – functionality.

So the L – proline fluctuation are the reflects of system viability.

L – proline levels were estimated in plants motivated under normal or stress conditions. There were established the increasing of free proline in stress plant, both wild type and experimental forms. But there was difference between initial and resistant forms. The level of amino acid demonstrated rapid changes coordinated with rapid changes of environment conditions.

Upon repopulation in resistant cell lines, proline promotes detoxification of Na^+ and Cl^- ions.

1

2

1 Resistant cell line, on the Ba²⁺; 2. Control

The complexity and polygenic nature of salt and drought tolerance are factors contributing to the difficulties in breeding of tolerant forms. The modern technological approaches are being elaborated to obtain variants, with higher tolerance.

1

2

1. Resistance cell line, on the Cd²⁺; 2. Control

Under water stress, the action of proline is directed towards maintaining cellular water balance

The lack of knowledge of stress associated metabolism remains, a gap in understanding; therefore efforts are currently in progress worldwide to estimate the genetic and molecular basis of complex trait. The implementation of *Nicotiana* investigations has been recognized in obtain forms with combined stress are already obtained. Further progress is anticipated by discovery more novel genes on a genome wide basis followed by determination of their physiological role in stress tolerance. The creation of advanced biological techies that can be used in significant nowadays.

A

B

A. Control and regenerant cultured under salinisation *in vitro*

B. Regenerant cultured under water stress conditions *in vitro*

1

2

C

D

E

C. Regenerants under lethal water stress (1) and in n.y. (2), Control (D) and regenerant (E) after a 5-day drought

Cell breeding using HMI is a new creative approach in plant biotechnology as a new scientific direction for solving practical problems for specialists in the agricultural industry, as well as for a wide range of people.

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